

**USED IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS TO INCREASE THE KNOWLEDGE
EFFICIENCY OF STUDENTS PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES**

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Abstract: In this article, information about the advantages of pedagogical technologies used to increase the knowledge efficiency of students in technology classes is sufficiently covered. In addition, the role of technology lessons in our lives and the use of modern technologies by pedagogues in technology lessons were discussed.

Key words: Innovative technology, pedagogical technology, master class, modern educational tools, electronic resources.

Today it is one of the most important tasks of our country to provide students with knowledge, education and training at the level of a qualified specialist, who will meet the demand of all-round mature, state educational standards. It is also important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching, to implement new informative pedagogical technologies in technology classes so that students can improve their cognitive efficiency and fully master the science of Technology.

In improving the effectiveness of knowledge of students, teachers are required pedagogical skills. It is also important to use textbooks, teaching and methodological manuals, handouts, electronic materials, layouts, use video rollers on technology science, perform learned working methods, use media tools to find terms in technology science, perform didactic tasks, be able to use information

sources (television, radio, audio-vedio recording, telephone), follow media culture when opening.

The fact that educators use practical work in our technology classes gives a big positive result. Currently, the use of Information Communication Technologies in technology classes is a very effective method for pedagogical teachers. Because, previously, the process of preparing items for students in the process of practical training in technology lessons was shown by the teacher to prepare them for students one by one, which would also shape the skill of making necklaces with no more numbers to the excess time spent. Today, however, by presenting the vediodars of labor operations depicted through telivezor to the students, it allows the teacher to easily monitor the work of the students and also allows the level of knowledge of the students to increase.

Another important thing about the use of this method by pedagogical teachers is that the training performed by qualified locksmiths, carpenters, tailors, seamstresses and our craftsmen in various fields allows students to shape various labor skills in them by demonstrating “Master classes”, as well as to better set up vocational orientation work.

One of the priorities of our independent Uzbekistan is aimed at educating young people with the future of the country as knowledgeable, inventive, creative, spiritually competent. This great goal is embodied in the framework of reforms carried out in the educational system and continued consistently. Pedagogical technology is a concept applied in the process of the field of technological development of pedagogical staff and education. Educational technology is an orderly sum of the most accessible and teaching tools of communication, information and management, which provides a means of achieving a guaranteed achievement in the educational goal and the intended results set in the current conditions and established time.

Pedagogical technology consists in a narrow sense-in the process of

mastering information, using it in practice, teaching them to create new information by opening up new meanings in them and various connections between information. And pedagogical technology in a broad sense is the sum of educational methods, methods and educational tools, it is a set of organizational and methodological tools of the pedagogical process. In general, pedagogical technology is a systematic legacy of the creation, application and identification of the entire process of teaching and mastering knowledge, taking into account the interaction of technical resources and people. When pedagogical technology is applied to the course of the lesson, the student's training in independent reading, knowledge, thinking to receive is strengthened. In this process, under the guidance of the teacher, the student independently receives knowledge, learns, assimilates. Therefore, pedagogical technology consists in the activity of influencing a person according to a predetermined goal. This included processes such as carrying out, organizing, conducting, improving, analyzing, generalizing, drawing conclusions, managing, controlling, evaluating activities.

In this case, it is advisable if, according to our own experiences, technology is based on educational technologies in organizing the practical work of students, taking into account the specificity of classes.

In conclusion, today, the teacher should not be limited to taking lessons on the basis of ready-made electronic resources, but to create educational resources, as well as modern technologies of teaching that put it into practice, to act as a person with the skills to effectively use opportunities, communicate the content of Science and knowledge that is part of it to students.

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